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PUBLIC POLICY OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES: EVOLUTIONS AND APPLICABILITY IN HEALTH IN THE STATE OF RIO DE JANEIRO.

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INTRODUCTION:

To understand the development of public policies aimed at People with Disabilities (PwD s), it is first necessary to understand the historical process of disability, its conceptual evolutions and the social movements around the issue. This article aims to bring a brief history of disability, as well as the construction of current public policies and the guarantee of the rights conquered along a difficult trajectory of exclusion and prejudice.

By following the historical context, we can observe changes in sociocultural behaviors and social movements that caused the transformations and paradigmatic concepts of what disability is today and how these changes gradually built and elaborated public policies aimed at People with Disabilities.

Despite historical data reporting the issue of disability since prehistory, a long period took place until the achievements of social rights.

In Brazil, the ratification of the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, in 2008, was the legal and historical landmark that consolidated the social perspective of disability, as well as the identification of who are the PwD in the country and the guarantee of the right to social protection of these subjects.

As a signatory to the United Nations (UN) Convention, Brazil has advanced in the implementation of public policies to guarantee the full and effective exercise of the legal capacity of people with disabilities in equal opportunities, valuing the role and choices of Brazilians with and without disabilities, with the launch of the National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Living without Limits through Decree 7,612, of November 17, 2011 (BRASIL, 2013). The proposal of Viver sem Limite is that the commitment assumed with the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities happens in people's lives, through the articulation of government policies for access to

education, social inclusion, health care and accessibility.

In the field of health, the Viver sem Limite Plan establishes the Care Network for People with Disabilities, aiming at the implementation, qualification and monitoring of rehabilitation actions in states and municipalities and their articulation between services, ensuring health promotion actions, early identification disability, disease prevention, treatment and rehabilitation. (BRAZIL, 2013).

The State of Rio de Janeiro, through the General Coordination for the Health of Persons with Disabilities , created its Care Network for Persons with Disabilities based on existing reference units, identifying them as possible services qualified to receive financial investment incentives. and costing. This made it possible, through the Ministry of Health, to enable the existing services, in addition to investment for construction, expansion and renovation. Such services were enabled by means of ordinances of the Ministry of Health, ensuring access and quality care to patients with physical, hearing, visual, intellectual disabilities and autism spectrum disorders (ASD), multiple disabilities and care for ostomy patients .

Complementing the advances in Public Policies aimed at People with Disabilities, in 2015 , LAW No. , under equal conditions, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by people with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and citizenship.

METHODOLOGY:

This article is categorized as a theoretical research with a qualitative approach, with an explanatory character within the historical-social context carried out by a bibliographic

review through books, scientific articles published in different national journals, laws, ordinances and decrees available in the databases online with a focus on the historical, social and rights analysis of people with disabilities.

DEVELOPMENT:

When researching the history of people with disabilities, we can find data from prehistoric life . According to Coma (1992) there are convictions that disabling diseases and physical disabilities are as old as life itself. Silva (1987) shows the existence of a complex system of beliefs and symbolisms involving individuals with disabilities . Continuing with the historical trajectory, in ancient Egypt the relationship between serious mental problems, physical disabilities and serious illnesses were associated with spiritual issues, where doctors believed that these conditions were caused by evil spirits, demons or sins of previous lives . Greece was considered the pioneer of medical care services for the general population and people with disabilities, when it implemented a system of care, initially aimed at the war maimed and later extended to other disabled people, regardless of the cause of the problem. (SILVA, 1987).

According to Roman law, the right to live was guaranteed only for children who did not present any signs of congenital malformation or serious diseases. Even with the right to legal infanticide, this practice was not carried out regularly, as it was up to the father to decide whether or not to execute it.

With Christianity and its creationist vision, the person with a disability also came to be seen as a creature of God and, therefore, possessing a soul and not deserving of punishment. Thus infanticide was no longer accepted.

In this way, the family and the church ensured care for the disabled person from a more pious and charitable perspective.

Renaissance period, between the 15th and 17th centuries, we had great advances based on a humanist philosophy and the first rights of men before society. The first signs of assistance to the PwD appeared. In England, King Henry VIII enacted the "Law of the Poor", by which all subjects were obliged to pay what was called the "charity fee", to continue the creation of hospital entities or organizations destined to the care of people with chronic problems or severely disabled for independent living (SILVA, 1987).

Society only adopted measures of assistance and protection for minorities and the marginalized, among them the PwD, in the 19th century, when in 1861, the United States began to guarantee housing and food to sailors and marines who acquired physical limitations. In 1867, the National Home for disabled volunteer soldiers was built in Philadelphia. (SILVA, 1987).

Some places in Europe also create specific places for the care and protection of PwD and the elderly and war disabled. We can cite as an example in 1872, in Denmark, the Society and Home for Cripples. Pioneering institution with the objective of helping people with disabilities to find an autonomous way to guarantee their livelihood, encouraging manual, artisanal and cooperative work among people with disabilities. (GARCIA, 2010).

Within the context of assistance programs and policies, we highlight the formation of the Welfare State in European countries after the Second World War, where policies aimed at serving the poor, the elderly, needy

children and people with disabilities began to be proposed, mainly war victims. In Great Britain, for example, in 1919, the Central Commission for the Care of the Disabled was created. (GARCIA, 2010).

The growing number of people with disabilities has become relevant in the internal politics of countries and with international proportions involving the United Nations (UN), as a consequence, on December 9, 1975, the Declaration of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities was approved, guaranteeing them in its third article the rights inherent to human equality. In 1981 the United Nations proclaimed The International Year of disabled Persons (International Year of Persons with Disabilities). (COSTA, 2008; FIGUEIRA, 2008).

Following the historical evolution, the UN approved the program of World Action for Persons with Disabilities (Resolution nº 37/52) on 12/03/1982, which has the principle of equal opportunities, guaranteeing access to the system for all disabled people. society – physical and cultural environment, housing, transport, social and health services, educational and work opportunities, cultural and social life, and even sports and leisure facilities, proclaiming the United Nations decade of disabled people, covering the years 1983 to 1992.

In Brazil, on the other hand, we can highlight the advance in the legal regulation of the social concept of disability in the first decades of the 21st century and with that, the adequacy of disability assessment for access to policies and services. The ratification of the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, in 2008, is the legal and historical landmark that consolidates the social perspective of disability, the definition of who the PwD are in the country and ensuring

the right to social protection of these subjects. (BARBOSA; DINIZ; SANTOS, 2010).

The social model appears in opposition to the biomedical model or the individual model of disability. For the biomedical model, disability is the result of a deviation in body functions and/or structures, and its treatment involves rehabilitation policies aimed at rescuing body functioning close to the functioning of those considered normal.

In the social model, people with disabilities suffer disadvantage because there is a culture of normality that privileges certain functionings to the detriment of others. By building the various social environments under an expectation of normality, the carnal order of humanity excludes the possibility of participation of people with disabilities. In this sense, disability is a system of inequality that must be addressed through inclusion and justice policies. (BARBOSA, BARROS, 2020)

Therefore, the social model considers that disability is an evolving concept and results from the interaction between people with disabilities and the barriers due to attitudes and the environment that prevent the full and effective participation of these people in society on an equal basis with others. (BRAZIL, 2009).

Aiming to advance in the implementation of public policies that would provide the full and effective exercise of the legal capacity of people with disabilities in equality of opportunities, valuing the protagonism and choices of Brazilians with and without disabilities, the National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Living without Limits, was launched through Decree 7,612, of November 17, 2011 (BRASIL, 2013). Emphasizing Brazil's

commitment to the prerogatives of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, ratified in Brazil with equivalent constitutional amendment. The proposal of Viver sem Limite is that the commitment assumed with the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities happens in people's lives, through the articulation of government policies for access to education, social inclusion, health care and accessibility.

Aiming to implement health actions determined by the Viver sem Limite Program, the federal government created in 2012 the Care Network for People with Disabilities, instituting the GM/MS Ordinance No. 793 of April 24, 2012 and No. 835 of April 25, 2012, legal framework for the beginning of the implementation of the Care Network for Persons with Disabilities (RCPD). Providing the implementation, qualification and monitoring of rehabilitation actions in states and municipalities and their articulation between services, ensuring health promotion actions, early identification of deficiencies, disease prevention, treatment and rehabilitation. (BRAZIL, 2013).

These ordinances were later updated by the MS/GM Consolidation Ordinance No. 3 of September 28, 2017, which consolidates the rules on the networks of the Unified Health System and No. 6, of September 28, 2017, which describes the financing rules and the transfer of federal resources for the actions and health services of the Unified Health System.

In parallel with the decrees and ordinances implemented in the field of health, in a dynamic process of consolidation of the social model of disability in Brazil, in 2015 the LAW No. which it describes in its article 1:

Art. 1 The Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities (Statute of Persons with Disabilities) is instituted, aimed at ensuring and promoting, on equal terms, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by persons with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and citizenship. (BRAZIL, 2015)

This article aims to highlight the experience of structuring the public policy of PwD in health, describing the process of structuring the Care Network for Persons with Disabilities (RCPD) in the State of Rio de Janeiro, where the care structure until 2011 was focused on the rehabilitation process, through the agreement of single modality rehabilitation services, that is, only in the physical, auditory and visual modalities and dispensing of orthoses, prostheses and means of locomotion, all funded by means of the medium and high financial ceiling complexity (MAC ceiling) (GOV. ERJ, 2020). As of 2013, in accordance with current ordinances, the structuring of the Network continued with municipal services that already performed some type of rehabilitation service and that were already recognized as a reference. The General Coordination of Health for People with Disabilities/DAPES/SAS/MS (CGSPD/MS) at the end of 2013, identified the possible services that could be enabled to receive financial investment and funding incentives, thus enabling the enabling of existing services, in addition to investment for construction, expansion and renovation. In December of the same year, ordinances were published referring to the qualification of these services and construction of new ones, as well as the structuring of the 1st State Conductor Group of the RCPD through CIB-RJ Resolution No. 2.457 of September 25, 2013. (GOV, ERJ, 2020).

RCPD's Mission is to implement Specialized Rehabilitation Centers (CER) and Orthopedic Workshops, thus ensuring access and quality care to patients with physical, hearing, visual, intellectual and autism spectrum disorders (ASD), multiple disabilities and care for ostomy patients.

Its Vision consists of including People with Disabilities in the provision of articulated and agreed care among the points of attention of the RCPD, stimulating their integration and their leading role in the economic, political and social context within the state of Rio de Janeiro.

And its Values are: Integrality of Care, Equity, Respect for the patient, Social inclusion, Autonomy, Innovation in health, its technical collaborators, supporters and managers of the three instances of the federation. It is important to highlight that the General State Health Coordination of PwD understands that the RCPD Vision should be revised according to its progress in the State of Rio de Janeiro. (GOV, ERJ, 2020).

The technical area and the coordination of the RCPD in the State of Rio de Janeiro, considers that in recent years, from the period of implementation of the RCPD to the present moment, that the services enabled in the Network model have matured and expanded their offer, adjusting their services aimed at for this logic, calibrating the quality of care for this public and, in a way, building the network flow between single modality services and CERs for the structuring of the care logic at the regional level (GOV, ERJ, 2020).

CONCLUSION:

Despite the long trajectory, the advances achieved, such as in the

establishment of a national policy for the integration of people with disabilities, in the legal constitution of general norms and basic criteria for the promotion of accessibility, there is still a huge gap between what the law determines and its effectiveness, as it is necessary to minimize and eliminate attitudinal barriers in order to overcome prejudice and exclusion.

REFERENCES :

BARBOSA, L.; BARROS, A.P; Studies on disability informing public policy: the experience of the University of Brasília in the construction of the Single Disability Assessment Model. In: Marivete Gesser , Geisa Leticia Kempfer Böck , Paula Helena Lopes (org.). Disability studies : anti -capacity and social emancipation. Curitiba: Ed. CRV, 2020, v. 1, p. 37-54

BARBOSA, L.; DINIZ, D.; SANTOS, W. Body Diversity and Medical Expertise in the Continued Payment Benefit. In: DINIZ, D.;MEDEIROS , M. et al. (Ed.). Disability and Equality . Brasília: Editora LetrasLivres : Editora UnB, 2010. p. 43-60.

BRAZIL _ Decree 6949, of August 25, 2009. Enacts the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and its Optional Protocol, signed in New York on March 30, 2007. Brasília: 2009.

BRAZIL , Decree 7612, of November 17, 2011 . National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities – Living without Limits.

BRAZIL , Ministry of Health. Ordinance GM/MS No. 793 of April 24, 2012 . DOU Brasilia, 2012.

BRAZIL, Secretariat for Human Rights

of the Presidency of the Republic (SDH/PR) / National Secretariat for the Promotion of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (SNPD). Living without Limits – National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2013.

BRAZIL, LAW No. 13,146, of July 6, 2015 . DOU Brasilia, 2015.

BRAZIL, Ministry of Health . MS/ GM Consolidation Ordinance No. 3 of September 28, 2017, which consolidates the rules on the networks of the Unified Health System and No. 6, of September 28, 2017

COMA, JMR Primitive Medicines, Paleomedicine and Paleopathology . Munibe Anthropology , n. 8, p. 63-79, 1992.

COSTA, SM de B. Human dignity and people with disabilities : legal and labor aspects. Sao Paulo: LTr . 2008

FIGUEIRA, E. Walking in silence: an introduction to the trajectory of people with disabilities in the History of Brazil. 1.ed. Sao Paulo: Giz, 2008.

GARCIA, VG Disabled people and the labor market : historical and contemporary context. 2010. 205f. Thesis (Doctorate in Economic Development) Institute of Economics, State University of Campinas, Campinas, 2010.

RIO DE JANEIRO STATE GOVERNMENT , Rio de Janeiro State Health Department. State Plan for the Care Network for People with Disabilities, November 2020

UNITED NATIONS ORGANIZATION. Declaration of the rights of disabled persons : resolution approved by the General Assembly of the United Nations, on 09/12/1975. Available at:

< [http:// portal.mec.gov.br/ seesp / arquivos/ pdf /dec_def.pdf](http://portal.mec.gov.br/seesp/arquivos/pdf/dec_def.pdf)>. Accessed on: 04/20/2022.

MARTINS, BS Disability and biomedicine: the body and the struggles for meaning. In: **MORAES, M.;MARTINS , BS** et al. (ed.). *Disability in Question : towards a crisis of normality*. Rio de Janeiro: Nau, 2017.

SILVA, OM da. *The ignored epic : the disabled person in the history of the world of yesterday and today*. Sao Paulo: Cedas, 1987.